

Fabrication of Mg-Zn-Ca metallic glass thinfilms by Ion assisted pulsed magnetron sputtering for Biodegradable implants

K.S. Abisegapriyan, B. Subramanian*

CSIR - Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu

Abstract

Ternary Mg–Zn–Ca thin film metallic glasses (TFMG) showed attractive properties making it as potential degradable materials for surface modification of implants, especially compared to traditional crystalline Mg alloys. Mg-Zn-Ca thinfilms of thickness of about 3µm were fabricated using Ion assisted pulsed magnetron sputtering and the amorphous nature of the coatings were confirmed using XRD and TEM-SAED patterns. Nano hardness of 50 Gpa was measured using nanoindentation. In vitro degradation experiments including electrochemical measurements and immersion tests revealed that the zinc could elevate the corrosion potential of Mg in simulated body fluid (SBF) and reduce the degradation rate. As observed from the SEM the coatings were non hemolytic. The cytotoxicity evaluated on L-929 cells revealed that Mg-Zn-Ca TFMG did not induce toxicity in cells.

Keywords: Magnesium metallic glass, Sputtering, Biodegradable, cytotoxicity.

Reference

1. Li, Gittleson et al, Chem.Comm. 2017, 53(59): 8288-8291
2. Gao, Guan et al, Materials Letters 2011, 65(4): 691-693